

Data Dictionary

Constructs

Constructs (Source)	Item Code	Measurement items
Team Learning	TL1	People in our team often speak up to test assumptions about issues under discussion.
	TL2	Our team frequently seeks new information that leads us to make important changes.
	TL3	Our team members go out and get all the information they possibly can from others (e.g. customers, other teams, Internet etc).
	TL4	People in our team often teach each other new skills.
Team Reflexivity	TR1	The methods used by our team to get the job done are often discussed.
	TR2	Our team often reviews its objectives.
	TR3	We regularly discuss whether our team is working effectively together.
	TR4	Our team often reviews the ways we get the job done.
	TR5	We regularly take time to figure out ways to improve our team's work processes.
Team Cohesion	TC1	Members of our team would rather go out on their own than get together as a group.
	TC2	I am unhappy with the level of our team's desire to excel.
	TC3	Our team does not give me enough opportunities to improve my personal performance
	TC4	I do not like the way our team is managed.
Knowledge Sharing	KS1	I voluntarily share my know-how, information, and knowledge with other employees.
	KS2	I cooperate or communicate with other employees in teams or groups for sharing information and knowledge.
	KS3	I can freely access documents, information, and knowledge held by other groups within our team.
Team Structure	TS1	It is clear what each person in our team is supposed to do.
	TS2	Our team members are sure about what they are expected to do.
	TS3	Our team leader makes sure that the team has clear, explicit expectations for its performance.
	TS4	It is clear to our team members what work goals and objectives are most important—we have a good sense of the priorities of our goals.

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Control Variables

Variable	Variable Name	Data Type	Description
Control (Team Size)	Team_Size	Numerical	How many people are there in your team? (1 = 1- 5 2 = 6 - 10 3 = 10 - 15 4 = 15 - 20 5 = 20+)
	team_size	Binary	Main Control Variable: 1 if team size is between 6 to 10 else 0.
	team_size_1	Binary	Robustness Check: 1 if team size is larger than 10 else 0.
	team_size_2	Binary	Robustness Check: 1 if team size is 10 or smaller else 0.
Control. (Experience)	Experience	Numerical	How many years of software development experience do you have? (1 = <1 Year 2 = 1 - 2 Years 3 = 2 - 3 Years 4 = 3 - 4 Years 5 = 4+ Years)
	experience	Binary	Main Control Variable: 1 if Experience is more than 4 years else 0.
	experience_1	Binary	Robustness check: 1 if Experience is more than 3 years else 0 performance.
	experience_2	Binary	Robustness check: 1 if Experience is less than or equal to 3 years else 0.
Filter	Agile_familiarity	Binary	How would you rate your level of familiarity with agile methodologies? (0 if not familiar at all else 1)